

ARDUINO BASED RADAR SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a Radar System controlled by an Arduino microcontroller. The RADAR system uses an ultrasonic sensor and servo motor as its main components to detect objects within a defined range. The ultrasonic sensor attaches to the servo motor, which rotates approximately 180 degrees to provide a visual representation of detected objects on the Processing IDE software. The Processing IDE graphically represents the angle, position, and distance of detected objects. An Arduino UNO board controls the ultrasonic sensor and interfaces the sensor with the display device. Research revealed existing navigation and obstacle detection systems and applications efficiently employing ultrasonic sensors. This low-cost RADAR system suitably applies to various navigation, positioning, object identification, mapping, tracking, and spying applications, including indoor environments.

KEYWORDS

Arduino, ultra-sonic, radar, positioning, surveillance, obstacle detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

A RADAR system functions as an apparatus for detecting or tracking objects by employing radio waves to determine their range, height, heading, or speed. Systems of this nature come in diverse sizes, each possessing unique performance characteristics. Certain radars find application in air traffic control at airports, while others serve in long-range surveillance and early-warning systems. Various methods exist for presenting information on radar operation, and there are customized radar systems equipped with advanced technology to enhance their operational capabilities. These enhanced systems find utility at elevated levels for the acquisition or extraction of valuable data.

The operational concept of our proposed system revolves around a series of interconnected components. Specifically, an ultrasonic sensor is intricately linked to the digital input and output pins of a microcontroller (Arduino, in our case). Additionally, a servo motor is incorporated into the system, connected to both digital output and input pins. The simultaneous connection of our two primary components, the ultrasonic sensor and servo motor, ensures synchronized

functionality. As the servo motor undergoes a rotational movement spanning from 0 to 180 degrees, ranging from extreme right to extreme left, it executes rotations around its axis. To visualize and convey the acquired data, including distance and angle information, we employ a computer screen. The presentation of this information is facilitated through a software application known as the "Processing Development Environment."

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

After reviewing several papers regarding the implementation of ultrasonic sensors and ARDUINO, it was evident that this concept is widely explored and remains a popular idea that is still evolving. The technologies employed were not only efficient and reliable but also economically viable. Additionally, the paper delves into other valuable applications of ultrasonic sensors. It specifically discusses a monitoring system designed to measure wave speed and river height using an ultrasonic sensor connected to a microcontroller (Arduino). The aim is to preemptively detect rising water levels and monitor speed, preventing potential floods or surges. The testing phase, focused on a simple water level scenario, demonstrated an accuracy of 96.6% with ultrasonics. However, when applied to rivers, errors surfaced due to varying water levels caused by waves, water speed, and floating objects. Unlike previous tests, the analysis in this paper emphasizes improvements in water speed tracking and floodwater level. Further research intends to transmit depth and speed information to a database server website for regular monitoring.

Another aspect covered in this research introduces an intelligent driver monitoring and vehicle control system to prevent accidents by monitoring driver activities. Common accident factors, such as alcohol consumption, carelessness, drowsiness, or medical conditions, are addressed. Various units in the system, including motors, relays, power units, and the ESP8299 module, were tested and found to be operational. An ultrasonic sensor alerts the driver to approaching vehicles, and the driver's status is monitored through in-vehicle sensors, with details updated to the owner. This system outperforms other technologies in terms of effectiveness, efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and time consumption.

The third paper in this research provides information on radio wave detection and tracking through a radar set, comprised of components like an ultrasonic sensor, a servo motor, and an Arduino. The linear measurement problem hindering distance measurement between objects is overcome with the introduction of an ultrasonic distance measurer. This radar system significantly reduces power consumption and efficiently tracks obstacles' distance and angle, displaying results on a monitor screen. The ultrasonic sensor, attached to the servo motor, detects obstacles across a 0 to 180-degree range. Both the ultrasonic sensor and servo are powered and controlled by the Arduino. The graphical user interface (GUI) is developed using the JAVA programming language to present the results on the monitor. The paper outlines a system for obstacle detection in a familiar environment, particularly catering to visually impaired individuals. The system operates through an Android-based mobile camera and employs an algorithm for real-time obstacle detection with a 96% accuracy rate. The proposed algorithm focuses on indoor mapping, considering different floors and storing reference images for each floor. Various techniques, including SONAR sensors and laser cameras, are discussed as viable approaches for obstacle detection. The paper introduces an algorithm for identifying obstacles in a known environment using an Android-based mobile camera that scans the designated area for obstacle detection.

This study focuses on the development of a walking stick tailored for individuals with visual impairment, enabling them to navigate obstacles and recognize currency. For the visually impaired, distinguishing currency or unexpected obstacles poses a challenging task. While size-based identification of currency notes may be feasible, determining their authenticity is considerably difficult. To address this challenge, the researchers have introduced the Currency Recognition Blind Walking Stick. While existing technologies employ optical character recognition, SURF, and color pattern extraction for currency recognition and obstacle detection, none of these systems specifically cater to obstacle detection for the visually impaired. Consequently, this framework stands out by offering an additional feature to assist individuals with visual impairment, making it more efficient than other existing solutions.

3. METHODOLOGY

To validate the functionality of this system, following its design, construction, and programming phases, we positioned several objects in front of the ultrasonic sensor. As the motor initiated rotation, the output was displayed on our monitor through the Processing IDE. Consequently, as the sensor encountered each object, a red segment appeared on the display indicating the distance and angle where the object was located.

For the initial test, an object was positioned at a distance of 30.5cm, as measured with a ruler. The system recorded the distance as 32cm. Subsequently, a second object was placed 20cm away, and the system registered it at 21cm. The calculated efficiency of the system from these tests turned out to be 95%.

System Overview:

Figure 1. System hardware description

The provided diagram offers a concise depiction of the radar system. As illustrated, we employ Arduino as the controller, utilizing an Ultrasonic sensor for input and a servo motor for output with a rotational capacity of 180 degrees. The microcontroller oversees all system operations, managing motor rotation, ultrasonic obstacle detection, and the presentation of results on the screen.

System Block Diagram:

Figure 2. Block Diagram of Radar System

Figure 2 provides an illustration of the block diagram for the system. It elucidates the workflow within this radar system. The sensor detects obstacles, discerns the incident angle, and calculates the distance from the radar. Simultaneously, the servo motor continuously oscillates, causing the sensor to move. The acquired data is encoded and transmitted to the Processing IDE, which visually represents it on the screen. The subsequent section of this paper expounds on the displayed results. All these operations are orchestrated by the Arduino microcontroller, encompassing the servo rotation, sensor data collection, encoding, and display transmission.

4. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The fundamental objective of our design is to determine the distance, position, and speed of an obstacle placed at a certain distance from the sensor. The ultrasonic sensor emits ultrasonic waves in various directions by rotating with the assistance of servo motors. These waves travel through the air and, upon striking an object, are reflected back. The sensor detects the returning waves, analyzes their characteristics, and outputs the results on the screen, indicating parameters such as the distance and position of the object.

The Arduino IDE is employed for coding, and the code is uploaded to the Arduino, enabling us to ascertain the position or angle of the servo motor. This information is then communicated through the serial port, including the measured distance to the nearest object in its path. The output of this entire process is displayed in the Processing software, presenting both input and output data, along with the range of the detected object. The sensor implementations are designed so that the ultrasonic sensor is mounted on top of the servo motor, as it needs to detect the object and its distance. The Arduino microcontroller oversees and controls both the ultrasonic sensor and the servo motor, providing power to both through the microcontroller.

Figure 3. Flowchart of Radar System

The provided flowchart elucidates the operational and decision-making sequence of this framework. The system initiation involves an input phase, where the ultrasonic sensor detects the presence or absence of an object. In any condition, whether an object is detected or not, the encoder relays this information to the controller while the servo maintains a continuous rotation. Upon detection of an obstacle by the ultrasonic sensor, the controller promptly processes the data, which is then transmitted to the IDE for display on the screen. The process concludes with an output, presenting the estimated distance of the object from the system and the angle at which it is positioned.

5. DISCUSSION AND RESULT

In this research paper, we detailed the design of our system, incorporating essential components such as a servo motor, an ultrasonic sensor, and a microcontroller (Arduino). The primary goal of the system is to track both the distance and angle of objects and graphically represent this information. The desired output is in graphical form, achieved through the utilization of processing software. The efficiency of our radar system can be gauged through testing objects at various distances to observe how swiftly and accurately it detects obstacles and provides an anticipated range. The accompanying figure illustrates the results displayed on the monitor screen of our design as the sensor rotates through the area, identifying obstacles along the way. The red area on the screen signifies the presence of an obstacle, with details below indicating the incident angle and distance.

Testing of the system

- I. Object 1 is placed 30.5 far from the radar, radar gives the distance 32 cm, so:
 1. $\text{error} = ((32-30.5)/30.5) * 100 = 4.918\%$
 2. $\text{efficiency } 1 = (100-\text{error}) = 95.08\%$

Figure 4. The Processing IDE screen showcases the output of the system, demonstrating the results obtained through our testing by placing objects

II. Object 2 is placed 20.3cm far from the radar, radar gives the distance 21 cm, so:

3. $\text{error} = ((21-20.3)/20.3) * 100 = 3.44\%$

4. $\text{efficiency } 2 = (100-\text{error}) = 96.55\%$

Figure 5. The Processing IDE screen showcases the output of the system, demonstrating the results obtained through our testing by placing objects

After the observations and calculations, we can conclude that this system is 95.815% efficient.

6. APPLICATIONS

1. Obstacle Detection and Avoidance:

- The radar system can be employed in robotics and autonomous vehicles for obstacle detection and avoidance. It helps in creating navigation systems that enable robots or vehicles to navigate through dynamic environments by detecting obstacles in real-time.

2. Security Systems:

- The radar system can be integrated into security systems to monitor and detect unauthorized movements in restricted areas. It enhances perimeter security by providing early warnings of intrusions.

3. Environmental Monitoring:

- The radar system can be utilized for environmental monitoring, such as measuring the water level in rivers or detecting landslides. It aids in collecting data for assessing environmental conditions.

4. Smart Agriculture:

- In agriculture, the radar system can assist in monitoring crop health and growth by detecting anomalies or changes in the field. It can contribute to precision agriculture practices.

5. Traffic Monitoring and Management:

- The radar system can be used in traffic management systems to monitor traffic flow, detect congestion, and optimize traffic signals for better traffic control.

6. Search and Rescue Operations:

- In search and rescue missions, the radar system can be deployed to locate individuals or objects in challenging terrains, providing valuable assistance in emergency situations.

7. Industrial Automation:

- The radar system can play a role in industrial automation for detecting the presence of objects on conveyor belts or in manufacturing processes, ensuring smooth and efficient operations.

8. Weather Monitoring:

- Radar systems can be adapted for weather monitoring applications, such as measuring rainfall, detecting storms, or monitoring atmospheric conditions.

9. Healthcare:

- In healthcare, radar technology can be used for monitoring patient movements or detecting falls, especially in eldercare facilities, contributing to improved patient safety.

10. Gesture Recognition:

- The radar system can be applied for gesture recognition in human-computer interaction scenarios, allowing users to control devices or interfaces through hand gestures.

11. Mapping and Surveying:

- The radar system can be employed for mapping terrains or conducting surveys by measuring distances and angles, providing valuable data for geographic information systems (GIS).

7. CONCLUSIONS

Various advanced control methods empower designers to exert greater control over diverse applications. In our paper, we evaluated the recommended mapping method for the entire system on a small scale. The chosen field for our "Radar System" design is extensive, presenting a high future scope for this technology. The applications of radar systems are vast and continually expanding, offering numerous possibilities. The design's future potential is particularly promising due to its security capabilities, allowing implementation across various applications. Additionally, the framework can be adapted or enhanced based on emerging needs and demands.

Given that our design focuses on a short-range radar, our research was specific and limited. The system is designed to detect objects within the range of 0 to 180 degrees, constrained by the rotational capacity of the servo motor used. Consequently, our design is not applicable to larger-scale obstacle detection in broader areas. To overcome this limitation, incorporating a 360-degree rotating servo motor could significantly enhance the system's efficiency. Future modifications may involve utilizing a higher-ranged ultrasonic sensor and implementing additional features, such as

mobility, an integrated alarm system activated upon obstacle detection, and the development of an obstacle-avoiding robot with a surveillance system. These enhancements aim to broaden the system's capabilities and applications.

8. REFERENCES